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**Larysa Butko¹, Volodymyr Maslak¹,
Daria Vasylenko¹, Zhanna Osikovich²**

¹ Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, Kremenchuk, Ukraine

² Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Krakow, Poland

External Image of the Modern Library as a Strategic Task of its Management

Abstract: *Introduction.* In modern scientific research of the social communications in general and the library science in particular, the issues of forming the image of the modern library in accordance with the requirements of the today's life have recently become relevant. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the study is to consider the features and components of the external image of the modern library and develop recommendations for its improvement. The traditional set of general scientific principles (determinism, reflection, unity of opposites) and methods (formal-logical, conceptual and functional analysis, content analysis, synthesis, abstraction, etc.) are used to solve the research tasks. *Results.* The article elucidates the fundamental qualities of the library's image. The system of factors influencing the image of the modern library is determined. The components of the external image of the library are analyzed and recommendations for its improvement are highlighted. *Conclusions.* A positive image is the result of the effective activities, covering processes from the study of the public opinion, inquiries of the library service users, which should be based on the serious social research, to the implementation of these inquiries by influencing both employees and service consumers. It is impossible to separate from the previous image; it is necessary to provide its radically new interpretation. That is why the formation of the image of a modern library is appropriate to make on the basis of the clear positive components of the existing database with the addition of the new characteristics that meet modern realities that need to be rethought, interpreted within a new image concept.

Keywords: library, image, management, image qualities, components of the external image, public relations.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. Modern socio-cultural and political-economic changes in Ukrainian realities require transformations in the functioning of the library institutions and their management. Today's day makes new demands to the libraries, forcing them to adapt to the information and communication, needs of consumers of the library services. The most effective management system is the basis for stabilizing the library, its social stability, progressive development in a changing environment.

In the modern scientific research of the social communications in general and library science in particular, the issues of shaping the image of the modern library in accordance with today's requirements have recently become relevant.

All the reasons for the negative image of the library, highlighted in foreign librarianship, are international in nature, structured and crystallized by *M. Matveev* (2004), who classified them into socio-political, socio-economic, professional and educational, psychological, direct organization of the library, the reasons for literary-artistic nature (stereotypes created by writers, journalists and directors).

The formation of the image of the library is one of the priorities of its management. Despite the fact that the theory and practice of the socio-cultural activities have accumulated some experience in the application and implementation of management in this area, but till now there is no fundamental, thorough research of the use of management technologies to shape the image of the library.

In Ukraine, management in general has not been as developed as in the leading foreign countries. We can safely say that it is on the path of formation, especially in the field of socio-cultural activities, adapting to the domestic realities the most relevant developments of the leading experts in the field of management. However, it is completely natural to have a number of problems characteristic of the period of formation, which has been repeatedly emphasized in scientific research (Bozhko, 2009; Dain, 1983; Ilhanaieva & Slobodianyuk, 1998; Martynyshyn & Kovalenko, 2018).

The management of the socio-cultural sphere has even more unresolved problems, due to its versatility and specificity. Firstly, the culture is an open complex diffuse system, characterized by weak structure, high subjectivity, and low predictability. Secondly, in the management of the socio-cultural sphere

it is necessary to optimize the development of its objectively valuable elements, based on axiological methods of cognition and orientation, as well as to take into account the inertia of culture and the strength of traditions. Thirdly, the effectiveness of the socio-cultural management does not fit into the framework of the economic indicators and is mainly non-economic in nature, which very significantly distinguishes culture as an object of government from other spheres of society. Fourthly, in the management of the socio-cultural sphere, the object of management simultaneously falls into the context of management, the very methods, forms and technologies of management are accumulated by culture and absorbed by it. Fifthly, culture as the most reflective sphere contains its own reflections, it is itself a mechanism of management in relation to itself and to people who are included in it and involved in it, not only offering a choice of creative models of reflection of reality, but also introducing fundamentally important values (Kasatkina, 2011).

State study of the problem. In the foreign science, the image of the library, prestige and status of the library profession began to pay attention in the second half of the XX century (Dain, 1983; Frylinck, 1994). Studies of Ukrainian science of these issues intensified only in the XXI century, in addition, they have a non-systematic, fragmentary nature (Samokhina, n.d., Kuharenko, 2014). Studies of Ukrainian science of these issues intensified only in the XXI century, in addition, they have a non-systematic, fragmentary nature.

In domestic science, library management is actively studied by N. Bozhko (2009), B. Bocharov and M. Voevodina (2006), O. Voskoboinikova-Huzieva and A. Brovkina (2003), V. Ilhanaieva and M. Slobodianyuk (1998), N. Kartashov (2002) and other scientists.

Foreign research of the issues related to the image of the organization, are actively conducted in both theoretical and methodological and applied areas (Kotler, 1998; Matveev, 2004; Pryanishnikov, 2010; Harlow, 1976). Also in the foreign theory and practice of the library science the relation to image of the library as to a cultural factor of organizational development is investigated (Moly, 2007; Frylinck, 1994).

Works are also important for understanding the essence and nature of library structure management T. Vylehzhhanina (2009), M. Kolesnikova and V. Kreidenko (2018), T. Kuliieva (2015), Ya. Martynyshyn and O. Khlystun (2019), N. Pryanishnikov (2010), T. Povalii (2019) and others.

Researchers emphasize the need for the active implementation of the modern technologies, tools and methods in library management, change management style, application of the innovative approaches to the organization of its activities, change traditional management systems to more efficient

and dynamic divisional and matrix, ensuring rapid and effective development of the library.

Unresolved issues. The need for the theoretical and methodological study of the problems of the library's image and the development of the practical recommendations for its improvement is due, in our opinion, to such factors as:

- firstly, deep crisis processes of the library business;
- secondly, the growth of the consumer demands for the library services as a result of raising the cultural level of the population;
- thirdly, the emergence of the latest trends in the organizational system of the library institutions;
- fourthly, competition between libraries in terms of attracting the most highly qualified staff.

According to the definition of *Ph. Kotler* (1998), who confirmed, that the image was the perception of the organization or its products by society (p. 23), without claiming absolute certainty in the definition of this concept, we propose the image of the library to understand its stable image formed in a certain historical period in the minds of different groups of its target audience.

When defining the image, the external image is traditionally distinguished, i.e. the image perceived by the subjects from the outside, from the external environment, and internal, i.e. the image perceived by the internal environment, for example, employees of the organization.

We can talk about the relationship and interaction of external and internal images, because, on the one hand, the success of the organization makes it attractive to potential employees and, consequently, allows to attract the most professional employees, on the other – it depends on the level of professionalism organization, its economic growth, attractiveness to customers, partners, donors, etc.

The library should aim to form a positive stable personal attitude to themselves and their services, to achieve mutual understanding with different social groups, because any organization that seeks to be successful needs self-presentation.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose of the article is to consider the features and components of the external image of a modern library and develop recommendations for its improvement, which will help create a reliable methodology for building a positive image of the library organization and, as a result, addressing pressing issues of its management.

To achieve this goal, you need to solve the following tasks:

- to outline the tasks and fundamental qualities of the library's image;

- to supplement the system of the factors influencing the image of a modern library;
- to develop a system of the factors that play a role in shaping the external image of the library;
- to develop recommendations for improving the logistics of the library in modern conditions;
- to identify the tools of the public relations that will contribute to the formation of a positive image of the library.

The methodological basis of the study: functional concept of the culture, which defines it as a universal property of the social life and as the basis of the personal development of a man; the concept of modern society, which states changes in the mental components of the modern culture, ways of presenting socio-cultural values; management concept based on the definition of the management principles and tools. The image of the library is explored from the standpoint of a systems approach, according to which it is a complex, open, plastic system consisting of the interconnected and interacting elements, united by a common goal to improve the status of the library organization.

Research methods. To solve the problem of research, we used the traditional set of general scientific principles (determinism, reflection, unity of opposites) and methods (formal-logical, conceptual and functional analysis, content analysis, synthesis, abstraction, comparison of theoretical and empirical research on this issue, problematization, schematization, logical-deductive method).

These general scientific principles are necessary in the study of library management and modern image trends in the field of librarianship, identifying their genesis and basic characteristics.

Formal-logical method allows you to consider the existing definitions of image, to assess their advantages and disadvantages. Conceptual analysis, synthesis and abstraction are used in the study of domestic and foreign authors on the problem. The logical-deductive approach is due to the specifics of the material presented in the analytical part of the article.

Research information base. Library analysis of the problem of the image formation is based on a well-developed scientific basis for studying image as a social and cultural phenomenon, which was developed in research in the field of philosophy of culture, theory of organizations, social communication, general and social psychology, sociology.

Our own empirical research was based on the observations of library facilities in Poltava region of Ukraine for the period 2019-2020, the realization of their image potential, conducting surveys among employees of the library

institutions and consumers of library services, etc., resulting in recommendations for improving the external image library as a strategic task of its management.

Consideration of the image of the organization, in our case the library, in the Ukrainian humanities does not yet have a stable tradition. This is a new direction of scientific research, which follows from the sociological traditions of studying the attitude of social groups and communities to various social phenomena and social institutions.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Fundamental qualities of the image of the library and the factors affecting it

The image of the library performs the following tasks: representation of the library, i.e. informing about its mission, benefits, range of services, their quality, etc.; motivation to action, namely: attracting and retaining consumers of library services, partners, potential donors (*Figure 1*).

The following fundamental qualities of the library's image are distinguished as:

- informative, which consists the fact that the image contains information about the features of the library: its specialization, list of services, etc.;
- the expressiveness of the image is realized the fact that a significant amount of information about the object of perception of emotionally expressive color;
- voluntariness of image motivates to a certain social behavior;
- functionality is achieved by the effectiveness of the image, its effectiveness, ie the level and nature of the tasks;
- objectivity as an image quality is realized in the fact that any library has an image, regardless of whether it is generated consciously or formed spontaneously;
- objectivity as an image quality is realized in the fact that any library has an image, regardless of whether it is generated consciously or formed spontaneously;
- dynamism is that the image is active, mobile, requires constant monitoring, support, updating and depends on many factors;
- flexibility of the image is realized in the fact that it is plastic, capable of modification in accordance with changing economic, psychological, social conditions; the content of the image is structured according to the nature of social relations in which libraries are included and the conditions in which the people who perceive them are;

Figure 1. Factors affecting the image of the modern library

Source: author's scheme on the basis (Matveev, 2004)

- economy of the image contributes to the saving of material, financial resources, time;
- symbolism of the image involves the use of a certain image or system of images-symbols to represent the idea, which reveals the characteristics of the object and reproduces the idea of it;
- duality is revealed in the fact that the image of the library is formed by its activities, is a product of its activities, on the one hand, on the other – the library, its status, role in society is greatly influenced by socio-economic, political and cultural level of society);
- targeting is that the image is designed for specific people or a social group; the library may be perceived differently by different groups of the public, as the criteria of these groups in its perception differ);
- clarity of image implies that it must be clear to the recipient;
- completeness of the image is characterized by the integrity of perception;
- the synthetic image is due to its complexity, which involves the interaction of all components;
- validity implies validity, adequacy;
- openness of the image – this is its constant interaction with the environment;
- stereotyping of the image is that the image strategies are repeated, commonplace, generally accepted;
- publicity implies that the image is designed for a wide range of consumers of the library services, government officials, business structures.

Based on the developments of *M. Matveev* (2004), we clarify the following factors that affect the image of the modern library. Consider them in more detail. The system of activities carried out by the library to increase its

importance and attractiveness among consumers of library services, the local population in general, business and government officials, on whom the activities of the library depend. The next factor is the idea of the library as a socio-cultural institution, its activities that exist in society. Another equally important aspect is the reflection of the activities of libraries in works of literature and art: in fiction, movies, journalistic publications, theatrical productions, etc. (p. 13).

An important feature of the formation of the image of the library is also the policy of the state in the socio-cultural sphere, the level of state support of socio-cultural institutions, as well as the level of economic, political, social and cultural development of society.

The formation of the external image is influenced by the following factors: product quality and service; exterior and interior of the building, its location and landscaping of the surrounding area; comfort of the library environment; appearance of employees; financial stability; social policy (including participation in charity events); ability to maintain business relations with partners, users; advertising and public relations.

3.2. Material and technical base and tools of the public relations: recommendations for effective use

The economic and political situation in Ukraine makes it impossible to build libraries, and the technical requirements for the design and construction of libraries are extremely technically and morally outdated. Therefore, it can only be about repairing the library building and its premises, equipping the surrounding area and providing conditions for visiting the library of people with special needs.

The first thing that provides the external component of a modern library is the dangerous working conditions of librarians and visitors, compliance with sanitary and hygienic requirements, fire safety rules and more. In addition, the conditions should be comfortable.

International regulations stipulate that all library services must be physically accessible to all members of society. Therefore, the library should be conveniently located and have good reading and study rooms, technically equipped and work at a convenient time for users. It is assumed that it should also provide services to those users who cannot visit it (UNESCO, 1994).

The maintenance of the library building, the territory of its economic yard, operation of the equipment, etc. is regulated by the numerous regulations (Ministry of Labor and Social Policy of Ukraine, 1998; Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2017).

The material and technical base of the library, including the maintenance of its building, is entrusted to the owners, or founders, of the library: “funds, appropriate means of mechanization and automation of library processes, reproduction equipment, other equipment and transport is carried out by their owner (founder)” (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2017).

At the expense of the state and local budgets financing of development and realization of the programs of development of library business, construction and reconstruction of library buildings, constructions, rooms, development of remote service by means of telecommunications, other forms of service of inhabitants of remote areas, persons with special needs is carried out.

All over the world, according to *M. Pryanishnikov* (2010), the library is no longer considered a box or container with books, the quality of the environment, the library's compliance with the humanitarian needs of the local community, its socio-cultural diversity came to the fore. Having ceased to be the object of simple management, it requires completely new, rather complex design methods (p. 21).

The new building of the library always demonstrates its demand in society as a whole and in a particular society, its status, above all, visualizes the invested resources. The new modern library building, like any manifestation of fashion, is characterized by respectability, elitism. Today, the global library community emphasizes a certain social stratification in which leaders and outsiders are determined by the presence or absence of a new building or design, modern equipment, specialized furniture, and so on.

The capabilities of the libraries in this regard are somewhat limited by today's realities, but it cannot be said that librarians are not able to influence the improvement of the interior and exterior of the library. In this regard, the cooperation of libraries with local authorities, enterprises, charitable foundations and other potential donors is extremely important.

In addition, today libraries have the opportunity to participate in different international and domestic programs to improve logistics, competitions for grants and more. It is clear that it requires the interest of the potential donors, actively promoting their services on the market. Libraries that innovatively organize their activities are active, interested in new opportunities, have the opportunity to improve their material and technical condition.

For a more professional approach to the organization of library space, we recommend conducting appropriate seminars, courses or inclusion in the components of the educational program of the specialty 029 “Information, Library and Archival Affairs” components “Architecture and Design of Libraries”, which will form relevant competencies, such as: ability to organize

and design a library space, apply modern trends of library design, its flexible planning, functional zoning, creating a visual image of the library, its corporate identity, etc.

In order to form a positive external image, it is necessary for librarians to interact with higher education institutions, actively applying a dual approach to the training of librarians (Maslak et al., 2018). It contributes not only to improving the efficiency of education, but also the formation of students' interest in the profession of librarian and, as a result, improving the quality of library staff, its “rejuvenation” due to specialists who understand modern information technology, demand of modern visitors and can satisfy it.

One of the most important factors in forming a positive image of the library, which is actively emphasized in modern scientific research in the library science, is public relations.

Public relations in relation to the library is defined as a special function of management, which aims to establish and maintain relationships, mutual understanding, mutual recognition and cooperation between the library and society; managing the process of solving problems or controversial issues; assisting management in studying and responding to public opinion; identify and emphasize the responsibility of management in matters of public interest; help management change effectively as time goes by; be a system of early warning, helping to anticipate development trends; use scientific methods based on the ethical norms of communication as their main means (Harlow, 1976).

In order to form a positive image of the library today, it is appropriate to use the following tools of public relations:

- active cooperation with the media, which involves the publication of materials about the activities of the library; organization of press conferences with media representatives, interviews and meetings with leading libraries; preparation of TV and radio programs; posting materials such as “What is read in the world today”, “Top world bestsellers” etc.;

- presentation of the library on the Internet, namely: preparation of a quality library site; maintaining pages in the most popular social networks; creating a YouTube channel; organization of online service;

- preparation of book exhibitions;

- organization and holding of socio-cultural events;

- providing library premises for conferences, seminars, trainings, courses, meetings with prominent figures of science, culture, politics, business;

- involvement of librarians in scientific activities;

- publishing activities, which mainly involves the preparation of bibliographic manuals;

- advertising activities: placement in organizations, educational institutions, enterprises on city lights, billboards, etc. library advertising;
- development of corporate style.

This approach will solve the current problems of library management to improve the external image and, as a result, will help promote the library and promote library services in today's information market.

4. Conclusions

The image cultivates the economic, social and cultural values of the library. The process of its formation is extremely complex and determined by the personal and ideological orientations of potential consumers of library services. Prestigious image contributes to raising the social status of consumers of library services, referring them to the level of social ladder to which they aspire: a person who visits the library has the status of cultural, successful, it is interested in the latest trends in culture and more.

As a result of the study, the following conclusions can be shown.

1. Modern socio-cultural and political-economic changes of Ukrainian realities require transformations in the functioning of library institutions, their management in terms of forming a positive image of the library institution.

2. The need for theoretical and methodological study of the image of the library and the development of the practical recommendations for its improvement due to deep crisis processes of librarianship, growing consumer demand for library services as a result of improving the cultural level of the population, the emergence of new trends in libraries attracting the most highly qualified employees.

3. The image of the library is defined as its stable image, formed in a certain historical period in the minds of different groups of its target audience.

3.1. Traditionally, the external image is distinguished, ie the image perceived by the subjects from the outside, from the external environment, and internal, ie the image perceived by the internal environment, for example, employees of the organization.

3.2. Tasks of the library image: representation of the library, ie informing about its mission, advantages, range of services, their quality, etc.; motivation to action, namely: attracting and retaining consumers of library services, partners, potential donors.

4. Positive image – the result of effective activities, covering processes from the study of public opinion, inquiries of consumers of library services, which should be based on serious social research, to the implementation of these inquiries by influencing both employees and consumers of services.

5. The following principal qualities of the library image are distinguished: informative, expressiveness, voluntariness, functionality, objectivity, efficiency, dynamism, flexibility, economy, symbolism, duality, addressability, clarity, completeness, syntheticity, validity, stereotype, publicity.

6. The image of a modern library is influenced by the following factors: the system of activities carried out by the library to increase its importance and attractiveness among consumers of library services, local people in general, business and government, on which the library depends; ideas about the library as a socio-cultural institution, about its activities that exist in society; reflection of the activity of libraries in works of literature and art: in fiction, movies, journalistic publications, theatrical productions, etc.; state policy in the socio-cultural sphere, the level of state support for socio-cultural institutions; level of economic, political, social and cultural development of society.

7. The formation of external image is influenced by the following factors: product quality and service; exterior and interior of the building, its location and landscaping of the surrounding area; comfort of the library environment; appearance of employees; financial stability; social policy (including participation in charity events); ability to maintain business relations with partners, users; advertising and public relations.

8. The material and technical base of the library is one of the most expressive elements of the external image of the library. It is clear that the capabilities of libraries in this regard are somewhat limited by today's realities, but its improvement is possible with active cooperation of libraries with local authorities, enterprises, charitable foundations and other potential donors, participation in various international and domestic programs to improve logistics, in competitions for grants, etc., an innovative approach to the organization of activities, interaction of library staff with higher education institutions.

9. The formation of a positive image of the library determines the active use of the full range of tools of public relations as one of the most important factors.

The scientific novelty of the research results is based on a systematic approach, understanding the essence of the image of the library as a strategic task of its management in the period of innovative transformation processes of the socio-cultural component of the modern society.

The practical significance of the obtained results are the formulated and offered scientific ideas, offers and conclusions can be used for the decision of actual problems of library management concerning improvement of external image and work of libraries in practical activity of the library organizations.

Prospects for further scientific exploration in this direction need further study of the tasks of library management in the formation of the internal image of the library. It influences the internal processes in the library organization

and is organically interconnected with the external image, which largely depends on the formation of external relations and business processes of the organization. In addition, the priority of human resources and the need for their activation has recently been postulated in foreign and domestic scientific intelligence.

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Information about the Authors:

Larysa Butko, Assoc. Professor, PhD, Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, Kremenchuk, Ukraine; e-mail: larysabutko@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8817-3381>

Volodymyr Maslak, Professor, DSc, Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, Kremenchuk, Ukraine; e-mail: vimaslak2017@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2898-2400>

Daria Vasylenko, Senior Lecturer, Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, 20 Pershotravneva Str., Kremenchuk 39600, Ukraine; e-mail: dvoloshka05@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9052-8287> (corresponding author)

Zhanna Osikovich, PhD, Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Krakow, Poland; e-mail: zanna.osikowicz@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1805-4651>